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STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE

GLOBAL HALLMARKS

(ONE CULTURE WITH GLOBAL PRESENCE)

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INTRODUCTION

“Archaeology only can mature when the philosopher and the archaeologist are the same person”

R. Bradley
1995

We are now living in an amazing period of scientific advancements, of investigation and discovery, archaeology is no exception to this. With easy access to research papers, maps, diagrams and photographs, it has become more and more apparent that some, if not most, of the older structures we find follow a set of rules. A specific matrix of design that is not accidental, nor is it the result of nearly, if not simultaneous, independent, localized developments in engineering and architecture, that happen to be the same or extremely similar.

This line of thought will present several satellite challenges to the main body of current academic perspectives. As we will demonstrate, there was a cultural singularity, perhaps not the only culture of the time, but it was nonetheless, one with presence in most, if not all inhabited continents. This alone implies in the very least, that humans have been travelling far and wide, long before what is considered possible today. However, this is not to be the first time an academic paradigm is proven wrong, nor will it be the last. The very scientific method makes it so, and no bad judgement should be given to its actions. After all, science, no matter what discipline we consider, can only produce as good an answer as the selection made from the considered data. Because of the vast amount of relevant arguments in favour of our hypothesis, in this Statement of Significance, we will present only a few examples which in themselves represent only a small fraction of the existing material corroborating our findings.

We are now pushing historical dates further back in time on a regular basis. In doing so, many taboos have been shattered, many concepts of human history have been rewritten. However, were we able to go back in time, these taboos and concepts would have been defended with ferocious tenacity, absolute certainty, or little to no doubt. This is but another one of those cases, and although we do not wish in any way to be labelled as the ones to threaten an old dogma, long in its years of deep thought, that is exactly what we are doing here, with the data presented in this S.O.S.

Since this is not an exercise about one aspect of one site, nor of one site but of many aspects within many sites and their common characteristics, we will present a selection of several locations, some still in their original form, some already repurposed and even some undiscovered that we expect are yet to be found. This will include caves, temples, palaces, pyramids, mounds, fortifications, underground sites, megalithic work and other type of structures. These, as we will demonstrate, share a set of characteristics and follow a number of laws, which make these locations fall, unequivocally, under one single mindset, one cultural orientation and one engineering perspective. On top of this, we add a clear demonstration of the intentionality of these locations' actual functionalities that are often, if not always, labelled as coincidence or perceived by its builders only after its construction and use.

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STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE

Before we dive into the data, it is important to realise that we must first have some sort of understanding of the mindset of this ancient global culture. This is required in order to better conceive in our minds what was their purpose, and no less interesting nor important, was this purpose worthy of the effort required to create such structures? We will show that the answers to these questions have not only a significant academic value, but that they have the potential to radically change our interpretation of the distant past cultures, whose wisdom presents itself as a path for the solution of current and future problems of our civilization and its survival, as it did many times in the past.

We do not presume to say that we have unravelled this mystery and in doing so, that we now have all the answers, we have not. However, what we will demonstrate is that these long known, and even longer ignored set of hallmarks, are not only important, but they are also paramount. This, in order for us to begin and realise the full extent of their importance, of their significance; is a crucial point leading us into a better understanding of the many structures we inherited from our distant ancestors to their full extent and functionality.

In order to do just that, we here expose the great value of what we called “Global Ancient Hallmarks” (GAH). A group of signature like statements, that due to their undeniable global presence, within the many different architectural shapes and forms, shows us the connection and even perhaps, the encoded information revealing the types of functionalities incorporated in their engineering. These GAH can be present singularly, or in different concepts, though there are several variations within each one of them as we shall demonstrate. For instance, “Nubs” being one of those hallmarks, do not stand alone, but are often, if not always, accompanied by other physical evidence markers that can also appear isolated in certain areas.

Recognizing its (GAH) presence all over the world is easy, for it depends only on a series of unmistakable characteristics, since these set it apart from the rest of the structure upon which they are placed. Their existence and incorporation within the architecture is, if nothing else, clearly intentional, requiring additional work in order to create them. However, as we will demonstrate beyond doubt, they are not decorative as some claim, but do indeed serve a purpose.

So what are these hallmarks?

1. *Frequencies*
2. *Telluric Currents*
3. *Astronomical Alignments*
4. *Nubs*
5. *Inverted Nubs*
6. *Bevel Edge Blocks*
7. *Bevel Edge Nub Blocks*
8. *Polygonal Stonework*
9. *Nubbed Polygonal Stonework*
10. *Lozenges*
11. *Fillerstones*
12. *Pinch Holes*
13. *Incised Motif (chakana/stair step motif)*
14. *Flightless Bird*
15. *Double serpent motif*
16. *Scrape Marks*
17. *Keystone cut blocks*

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Before understanding the implications of what these Global Ancient Hallmarks represent, it is very important to understand the variations of these hallmarks, since obviously, not all lumps, bumps, dimples, holes and protrusions constitute one of these architectural elements. Within this study, we will try to help others to understand not only the global implications of this specific set of markers, but also the importance they had on the local culture. A set of features that not only stands to this day implicit in its engineering, but they also clearly show us that these appear represented in historical sites in all four corners of the earth. These come from a long and fastidious compilation of evidence that are already represented in a comprehensive A to Z catalogue, part of which will be shown within this paper.

These hallmarks will be the main points of focus of this work, and we will stress why it is important to recognise its significance, not only locally, but globally. An assessment of their significance, of the implications and connections these hallmarks have, toward a number of scientific fields, which are essential and as such, they will be considered and reported within this paper. We will show beyond doubt, the vast quantity of examples in existence of these specific hallmarks, how they correlate, how we see them in the historical context, their cultural and social implications, and last but not least, their effects to the structure they appear in, and its surrounding landscapes.

Due to their importance, and since most have not yet been considered as relevant by the Academic world, we will attempt to show here what effects and implications these hallmarks have upon the current narrative of Archaeology and upon our understanding of the past. We will show if and how they correlate to the stars, revealed by patterns that are found in multiple countries. Also, where these specific markers were used, in a clear demonstration of a profound knowledge of the night sky that could perhaps be used to predict certain patterns, or periods of particular importance for the actual functionalities of a determined location. Because of the interdisciplinary scientific aspects of these hallmarks, that is in itself, a testament of their significance, since they can be explained and included into many different scientific disciplines. For instance, the petrology and mineralogy within these hallmarks and how they relate to archaeoacoustics and archeoastronomy. How these in turn work with natural vibrations and/or occurring frequencies, and therefore affect or create resonance within and around the temples they are situated on.

We will look into the quartz crystal content and typology at each and every site that has been studied within these contexts that, as we will show, imply these Hallmarks were related to a functional aspect and not just a stylish or architectural representation. Obviously, once the quartz crystal aspect was considered, it automatically led us into electrical and/or piezoelectric aspects that we are yet to fully comprehend. In fact, could there have been use of frequencies and harmonic resonance alongside some of the hallmarks to create functional aspects we do not yet understand? This paper will show those theories in detail and how the hallmarks could actually have been applied, used, and also, the possibility of them being guidelines, a forgotten ancient language or even some lost science.

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One way or another, and in consideration with the physical evidence we will provide, it will be clearly demonstrated to all, be them academically wise or independent researchers, that these hallmarks are far more important than most think or consider, and deserve to be looked upon, researched and decoded.

These hallmarks are of worldwide importance as one of the first, and most complex set of recognisable replicated features that can be found at the oldest of known structures, all the way into the modern Roman Era, and even more recently incorporated into religious buildings all over the globe. Their significance rises from the interrelationship of the various hallmark representations and the elements, (air, water, fire, earth, and the aether) that once studied, have the potential to be of great importance for our understanding of the past mindset and mindscape. Who will deny the immeasurable value of the existence of a global culture that influenced the ancient world? Even if it was to be proved wrong, a consequence of multiple unlikely coincidences, the existing known and catalogued examples, which can be found not locally, but across the entire planet, makes these hallmarks not only worthy of attention, but of some serious academic respect and research.

Key aspects of the Significance of the GAH include the following:

- The exceptionally high quality of each one of the Hallmarks, and general workmanship on all sites where they are found.
- The obvious relationship, perhaps interdependent of these hallmarks within each site, assumes several layers of significance, from the allowance of identification of the builders, to possible keys to the functions of the structures they are presented on.
- The especially important and quite unique fact that they appear on all inhabited continents, on both hemispheres. Once verified, it will be one of the major discoveries in the universe of archaeology and history.
- These hallmarks reveal clear, undeniable intention and purpose, since their representation requires further hours of hard work that could otherwise have been avoided; especially when we are speaking of the primal matter from which they are brought into existence, including stones with very high Mohs values. Moreover, and of no less importance, the scouting for their location, that implies the understanding of several layers of scientific knowledge, which are even today, outside the expertise of well learned academics
- They are found within the most astonishing displays of stonework known to us, sites and structures that even today, with all our present engineering prowess, we would find nigh on impossible to achieve, and yet the assumption that those that built them as primitives had access only to simple tools. That alone makes them a paramount subject deserving of clarification.

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- While the layout of these hallmarks is not unique or constant since it varies from structure to structure, their morphology is constant and instantly recognisable and relatable to all other sites where they appear.
- There is much to be learned from these hallmarks, from a possible form of encoded language or, at the very least, some form of encoded message or information. This data could vary in nature, though this will require further research in order to understand their meaning and/or subject.
- The importance of the existing surviving examples and their potential for further exploration, to add useful evidence bearing on its conception, design and functionality, within the global presence and vast extent of their use through time.
- Their significance is confirmed again by their multidisciplinary nature, once more proving their intentional existence and not as some random artefacts resulting of stone quarrying and or carving, as was already established above.
- From all that is exposed above, we cannot but realise that the study of these hallmarks have the potential to revolutionise our perception of the past, to reveal a new paradigm of understanding of human relations through intercontinental contact, trade and exchange of ideas, beliefs and technological prowess. These reasons are on their own, though far from being the only ones, why these hallmarks require recognition, study and active research from all the disciplines required for their understanding, as will be shown in the next chapter
- The contribution that is obtainable from the study and understanding of these hallmarks, is of extreme value to the emergence of a new insight into the history and culture of and yet to be recognised civilisation, that was either globally present, or capable of travelling the vastness of seas and lands, sharing their knowledge with all other nations. As we seen above, their presence is found, from the paleolithic to 500AD and perhaps both earlier or later

Ultimately, we aim to show the significance of these hallmarks, be it individually, or collectively, aggregating both the studies that have been done by ourselves, and combining it with several others that we will be referencing throughout this paper. This Statement of Significance will show, beyond doubt, these hallmarks as a meaningful part of our past, that deserve recognition and research. What is already known, discovered and researched, resulting in the vast amount of empirical evidence considered here, should result in this subject becoming one of great importance and global significance.

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ASSESSMENT OF VALUES

BACKGROUND

The mentioned hallmarks are characterised by their conformity to certain design elements, which make them a very cohesive group, regulated by a set of rules that we have yet to fully understand. As for the dating, since these elements are incorporated in the very structures they exist or originate upon, this will obviously be in accordance with the sites in which they appear. However, from our preliminary approach, we expect to find evidence of much older dates for some sites, while others will remain within the age appointed to them. As mentioned before, the study of these hallmarks, require a multidisciplinary method of analysis, incorporating an ever-growing list of disciplines. Our research has so far revealed the necessity of understanding the following 16 areas of study described below, and how they corroborate and work in a symbiotic way.

List of disciplines required for the study of the hallmarks:

- **Archaeology**
- **Archeoastronomy**
- **Archaeoacoustics**
- **Engineering**
- **Electromagnetism**
- **Geography**
- **Geology - Including:**
 - **Crystallography**
 - **Mineralogy**
 - **Piezoelectricity**
 - **Petrology**
- **History**
- **Hydrology - Including:**
 - **Cymatics (effects of frequencies on water)**
 - **River Systems**
 - **Underwater ways**
- **Magnetics - Including:**
 - **Anomalies**
 - **Earth Polarization**
 - **Magnetic Fields**
 - **Telluric Currents**
- **Mathematics**
- **Paleoclimatology**
- **Sacred Geometry**

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These hallmarks are not unique to one location, a country or even a continent, they are included in the very matrix of countless sites, from the oldest known to man, to some much more recent. They are always represented with at least one connection to the disciplines above, while most display several or even all of them. They are then far from unique, but no less important for it. On the contrary, they are the undeniable representation of one culture that by all means, still awaits to be unveiled. One that was present globally and at the very least, exerting their influence all over the world. As mentioned earlier, we already have a catalogue of these GAH that clearly attests to our claims in this respect.

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EXPOSING THE HALLMARKS

In this chapter we present a comprehensive guide to the hallmarks, something of vital importance, since most of them are absent from the historical record. Therefore, we demonstrate here exactly what they look like, their morphology and the most frequent nomenclature used for their identification, thus providing an easy means of their recognition. After which recognition, everyone, no matter their skill level or academic graduation, will be able to see how easily noticed these hallmarks actually are. So much so, that either on site, or through images as we will exhibit here, their presence and their significance is not only ; it raises questions as to how they could be ignored for so long, and by so many great academics and authors, that have otherwise shown us so much of the history and functionality of these sites and their features. Let us look at them one by one and into each variation that are represented within ancient structures:

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SOUND FREQUENCIES

“If a picture paints a thousand words, a sound-scape can paint a thousand pictures”

Glenn Kreisberg

Archaeology, although of paramount value to the understanding of the past, this discipline was found insufficient to explain all that was found and analysed through its long years of existence. New disciplines were added and through them, new facets of previously thought of well-known locations came to light. Among these disciplines, one of, if not the most important, is Archaeoacoustics. Through it, what was partially known only to a very select few, came once more into common knowledge.

“Archaeoacoustics is a complementary discipline of Archaeology and Anthropology which may help expand our understanding of why certain sites were considered sacred in ancient times. It is a new perspective to analyse archaeological sites which sometimes have interesting sound characteristics.”

Paolo Debertolis, Daniele Gullà, Francesca Piovesana, 2016

From the Macro-Cosmos to its opposite counterpart, frequencies are embedded, into the very Matrix of this reality and are most likely the connection to others that might exist. Sound has been a constant throughout all human existence. In more modern times it was mainly exploited as a recreational variant of mankind's culture, though that was not so in the distant past. From the most remote corners of time, sound was used for multiple purposes and actively explored and incorporated in all aspects of human life.

We find it incorporated in the oldest Shamanic practices, some of which have reached present times. From meditative states to transcendent consciousness awareness, to healing practices, sound or frequencies were a constant within the ancient mindset and a clear reflection of the landscape itself. Within the yet little understood achievements of megalithic architecture, where sound frequencies were not only incorporated, they are intrinsically connected to its edification and functionalities, we find a direct relation of cause and effect.

“After six years of experience of archaeoacoustic analysis in various sacred sites in Europe and Asia, we can confirm that every sacred site was chosen by ancient people for the extraordinary physical phenomena existing in those locations. These physical phenomena had a direct effect on human brain activity causing from an altered state of mind to a mystic ecstasy.”

Paolo Debertolis, Daniele Gullà, Francesca Piovesana, 2016

The fact that this is the first of all the hallmarks to be described here, is no coincidence. Due to the likeness of the sites where acoustic properties are found, this was deliberate and intentional

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Sound frequencies are, according to our own research, the key that connects all the Hallmarks here depicted and explained. While some sites have them as a natural occurrence, others are designed to be activated through the introduction of sound. However, the first type can also be enhanced by the addition of artificially induced frequencies. Additionally, there is clear evidence that there are different types of mineralogy, different concentrations of crystal, sometimes from site to site, sometimes within the site itself. All of which are part of the ancient technology used to create impressive locations, whose magnitude often blinds visitors and academics alike to its true wonders. Therefore it is only fair we treat each one as a different use of the same technology.

Beginnings

Thanks to the last 20 years of research, we now know of several descriptions and relics that testify to the importance of sound in ancient ceremonies performed in structures that were purposefully built for that effect. According to our current record of evidence, it began with the finding of locations which incorporated powerful echo capabilities..

Recent investigations into palaeolithic cave-art have revealed an association between areas which produce a strong resonance and the location of the art found.

This alone presents us with the fact that the properties of sound were being recognised, explored, appreciated and recorded almost 80,000 years ago, if not further back in time. From natural formations that were carved to enhance natural echoing properties, as we find in Baume Brune in France or Dry Fort Creek, in Utah, USA, to caves that were also worked in order to increase their acoustic properties, such as those found in the Mortero Gorge in Spain.

We then start seeing locations that are built from the ground up as the Long West Kennet complex, to huge areas carved into the underground bedrock as the Hal Saflieni Hypogeum.

Functionalities:

What we can say with comfortable certainty, is that to the likeness of current times, sound was used in the remote past, the same way we use it today and quite possibly, as we shall demonstrate, in some truly astonishing ways. Past cultures, exactly as we do, had a 3 dimensional world view, therefore sound was the main factor of their spiritual, technological and recreational way of life. Sound was used for the purpose of communication, entertainment, spirituality (creating altered states of consciousness), and even as an active (contrary to passive like a tall wall)) defence mechanism.

It was used outwardly, inwardly and centred. As we understand it, it was:

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- Directed into the heavens as a form of communication with the Gods
- Into the living plane as Hive connection for those under its influence, long distance communication, especially over water, and even as a weapon against enemies.
- On the underground or inward as an altering state of consciousness, and as a form to reach or communicate with other realms or the spirit world.

“After six years of experience of archaeoacoustic analysis in various sacred sites in Europe and Asia, we can confirm that every sacred site was chosen by ancient people for the extraordinary physical phenomena existing in those locations. These physical phenomena had a direct effect on human brain activity causing from an altered state of mind to a mystic ecstasy. There is no doubt that in Gropparello castle there are a great number of physical phenomena in all parts of the structure and in particular where the most ancient settlement was built: the ancient basement below the Roman guard tower.”

Paolo Debertolis, Daniele Gullà, Francesca Piovesana, 2016

Evidences for Long Distance Communications:

Humans have a long list of ways to communicate wirelessly through long distances that far exceed the visual horizon. For instance, the Yodelling tradition of the Alps is not a form of singing developed to entertain those that listen to this curious form of musical expression, it is in fact a form of long distance communication capable of relaying messages across the vast succession of mountains and valleys of that area. What most do not perceive is that although present day systems look extremely advanced when compared to those of the Stone Age, the truth is that although they use different means, they work through the same medium.

Either current technology or that of the distant past function under the same principles. For instance, if the correct frequency is not used and known on both ends, if the energy used is insufficient for the signal to travel, the communication will not happen, or it will fail to reach its destination. Therefore, any attempt to perform a long distance wireless communication requires a set of technological knowledge and execution in order for it to be successful. Our research shows that, contrary to our current cellphone frequency technology, the technology used by our distant ancestors was capable of reaching not only enormous distances, but also other realms of reality, time or existence.

Although we have not yet conducted our testing and therefore proven what we expect to be true, as some other recognized researchers have; there are clear indications that the earlier builders of the Malta structures developed a system capable of communicating across the Mediterranean ocean. We found a relay system capable of sending/receiving messages across the Mediterranean Sea. In fact, there are a number of similarly engineered semi-circular structures and towers, spread across the entire Mediterranean coastal areas, be them on European, or African coasts, thus explaining

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how communication was possible in real-time across great distances. An example are the structures we now find in ruins located on Lampedusa, a small island off the coast of Tunisia, North Africa. These megalithic remains are, to this day, unresearched. This type of communication was possible because sound seems to be amplified when it travels over water due to cool air, a principle that was obviously well known to the minds of those so-called primitive populations.

Sound Frequencies and Warfare

“Any severe and artificial extreme sound imposed on the sonic environment has a profoundly destabilizing effect on the individual, indeed infrasound has been used in the context of wars in the area of acoustic weapons”

Paolo Debertolis, Daniele Gullà, Francesca Piovesana, 2016

All those studies within archaeoacoustics have found two particular effects within the ancient sites with acoustic properties. These have been described as the sensations of awe and fear, that are repeated again and again throughout the studies we can find on this subject. In this chapter we will focus on the fear factor. From ancient myths to modern technology, sound, particularly infrasound, has been used as a weapon against foes or unwelcome visitors. Disorientation, dizziness and unreasonable and immobilizing fear are some of the results from the use of low, inaudible frequencies.

Our research has found several sites where academics expose these characteristics and their effects. Some locations, due to the architectural configuration can use and amplify ground vibrations to this effect, while others can do the same, but from artificially induced sound. In fact, we see infrasound being used for both awe and fear. It originates from the understanding that the ancients had of Scalar Waves. As we know today, low frequencies, when in an uncompressed state can lead to a state of bliss, of serenity and communion with others and the environment, that can sometimes be described as a hive mind within the communities that lived under its effects. However, once those same frequencies are compressed, once Scalar Waves are produced, a bubble of sound is created that renders those under its radius as helpless, discombobulated, terrified, incapable of thinking or coordination of their own movements. A terrible fear whose source was not identifiable made it even more powerful.

As a last note, the same structures that we described in the previous chapter, could use its communication capabilities, to disperse these compressed infrasounds in order to deter incoming threats be them arriving by sea or land. Some Academics relate this effect to the myths of the Sirens, since a few examples were found among islands that due to their size, would not have the numbers to resist pillage or conquest from invading naval fleets. Remember Sonchis of Sais and his report of the Atlanteans being defeated by the Hellenic people.

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Frequencies and Magnetic Vortexes

Researchers using the SRBG protocol have reported locations where the frequencies have the ability to create magnetic vortexes that are not randomly placed within these

structures, but specifically placed at every entrance point and in the very centre of the site. Moreover, if this was not impressive enough, these vortexes have the ability to change the brain of those that go through such places, tuning it and thus making all humans and animals that go through them vibrate into the same frequency, creating a global network of resonance, a sort of Hive mind connecting all life forms under its influence. Gropparello Castle, Italy, is one of such studied sites.

False Doors

During our research, we found several locations that display the necessary requisites to have incorporated within the very matrix of engineering, the creation of portals. Due to the lack of further investigation from academia, the locations require further study and testing to prove or disprove the actual physical existence of the portals. There is also the possibility that these portals might be real without existing in the physical plane, thus functioning as a form of mystical experience that although real, exists only to the individual/s that experience it within the many found active locations. The presence of this phenomenon was reported in academic studies on multiple sites, but they vary from appearing on orthostats, to false doors. This is an area of study that will require both will and courage to take it to a higher level of understanding. Be it real just in the mind of the test subject, or physical and visible to all, the implications on the technological, spiritual and ritualistic behaviour of our ancestors' culture and its achievements are enormous. An example of these experiments reported as below:

“In 2011, in order to study the possible effect of the passage resonance on a young initiate, an enthusiastic 14-year-old boy was used as a test subject. Late one summer evening, he sat alone in the W chamber in near darkness, as the passage was resonated. In the forecourt a skilled drummer played a miniature bass drum loudly with sticks, at a constant tempo of just over eight beats per second. The boy later reported that with eyes open, he could just make out the end stones of the W chamber, which at first appeared to be moving slightly. On one stone of the back wall a small black circle appeared, which grew in size; it took on the appearance of a passage leading to another chamber, which he thought he could see in to. He then continued to listen with eyes closed and was convinced that on two occasions someone had joined him in the chamber, but he had been entirely alone.”

Acoustics of the West Kennet Long Barrow, Avebury, Wiltshire
Steve Marshall. 2015

Psychologically speaking, we can assume that the right conditions were created in accordance with the Structure's functionalities. While the boy was, possibly by chance, in the right mindset for the experiment, easily reaching an altered state of

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consciousness, as for the musician playing in the forecourt, he was also performing the exact frequency of beats in order to activate the Barrow, that would in its turn produce the verified effects on the boy. We then conclude that the Site was being used correctly, and that at least one of its functionalities was successfully activated.

On the other hand, when Steve Marshall, the leader of the team researching the site, decided to use a different method while testing on himself, the results were quite different, as quoted below:

“I then experimented on myself using ‘binaural beats’. Two identical audible tones were fed to a pair of headphones, one tone to the left ear and the other to the right. The tones were tuned apart by 8.5 Hz, producing a regular beat frequency of 8.5 Hz between my two ears. After listening with closed eyes for about 10 minutes I suddenly had the powerful sensation of rising rapidly into the air! This was unexpected and very alarming. After only a second or so I panicked and dropped quickly to earth from what seemed to be a height of about 4 m. I resumed listening with eyes closed and after five minutes I felt myself ascending once more. The sensation was much milder, since I was prepared for it, and quickly passed.”

Same author, and paper as mentioned above.

Note that in that last report, things happened differently. Not only there was no sound introduced into the structure, the subject experience was dramatic, instead of contemplative. The sensation of being thrown into the air is to us a clear example of the site being wrongly used, with the experiment resulting in some sort of rejection, that can be translated into a bad experience, contrary to what happened with the boy.

Mineralogy

Sites like the Hal Saflieni Hypogeum, have no natural air vibrations or frequencies. It is made of limestone, with very little to no Crystal content at all, in contrast to the Tarxien Temples, which despite being just 200 metres away, and built with the same type of stone, have them in abundance. Another variation is seen in West Kennet Long Barrow, that was built with Sarsen Stones, with a staggering 98.5 to 99.5% crystal content by weight. This makes these stones not as such but as pure multi tonne crystals with an incredible level of purity. In comparison to another location where high crystal content stones were used, the Kings Chamber within the Great Pyramid has “only” about 65% of crystal content per weight. All of these sites have a tested and proven architecture and engineering that was deliberately developed to modulate, amplify and resonate sound waves in a specific fashion. What we deduce from this is that the Builders of such structures could create locations with Acoustic properties either using the present stone typology, or they would search, quarry and move the specific type of mineralogy required for their intentions along great distances, that would result in different practical functionalities.

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TELLURIC CURRENTS

The last two hallmarks require a longer explanation. They are present not in the structure itself, but these currents flow through the structure because of its placement within this planetary grid. This alone proves an ancient knowledge and technological skill that even today we do not fully understand. However, it is undeniable that not only did our distant ancestors know how to find them, they also knew how to differentiate and identify them. This is still beyond our current capabilities. These Currents are, so to speak, the power cables of the Planet that energize the landscapes of the world.

Sometimes called earth currents, telluric currents are a naturally occurring electric current flowing on and beneath the surface of the Earth. These energy lines are generally following a direction parallel to the Earth's surface. They arise from charges moving to attain equilibrium between regions of differing electric potentials; these differences are in their turn, set up by several conditions, including very low-frequency electromagnetic waves from space, particularly from the magnetosphere's effect upon the Earth's surface, and moving charged masses in the ionosphere and the atmosphere.

Some of the already identified lines of energy are:

- The Schumann Wave
- The Hartmann Grid
- The Curry Grid
- Ley Lines
- Vile Vortices
- The Becker & Hagens Grid
- The Black Lines
- The Potential Portals

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ASTRONOMICAL ALIGNMENTS

“What peoples throughout history and prehistory have made of the phenomena in the sky, how they used these phenomena and what role they played in their cultures.”

Sinclair, 2006

The modern scientific thought was late in realising that the megalithic culture was very well versed in astronomy. This happened thanks to the work of Prof. Alexander Thom highlighting this idea in the 1930s. However, it was not until 1954 that his first paper on the subject of prehistoric astronomy appeared. In 1967 he published a book called “Megalithic Sites in Britain”. In it, irrefutable evidence was shown of the application of astronomical knowledge. Hundreds of sites where this hallmark was present were, for the first time, exposed to the academic awareness. The ancient world was not so “dumb” as thought, or worse, we were not that advanced after all.

These alignments allow the tracking of the passage of celestial objects, not only the Sun and its rising and setting, but also of other celestial objects such as the moon, constellations and specific stars, even of planets. The empirical evidence comes from local observations done in situ, demonstrating the rise, transit and setting locations on the local horizon, and its changes during the seasons. Obviously, such observations allow the development of a local calendar that would predict and identify the most important moments during the year. For instance, the solstices and equinoxes of the solar movement seem to be especially of interest. Solstices occur midwinter and midsummer when the declination of the Sun reaches its minimum or maximum respectively. There are alignments of different orientation, nevertheless, what seems to be missing is the understanding that these precise mathematical calculations imply a much longer process of learning and gathering data, that far exceeds the timeline currently accepted by historians and academics alike.

Moreover, we suggest that this facet of ancient locations is intimately related to most, if not all other hallmarks. These alignments pinpoint specific moments in time, when the telluric currents are particularly strong. When connections to certain celestial points could be achieved, either through their combination with other hallmarks like frequencies, that then could take the subject or subjects into that very point, be it by psychological illusion or by actual transposition of matter

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NUBS

These appear in multiple forms, either isolated or in groups that sometimes include many of them displayed together. Therefore, when discussing this hallmark it is important to first understand the variations they present. With that in mind, we have standardised semi-circular, square, rectangular, and triangular versions. Usually they present themselves on blocks that can either have one, two, three and sometimes four, while the shapes can also vary on each block.

Many ideas have been brought forward in an attempt to explain these features, though seldom by academics. Academics usually refer to these as leftovers, or as anchor points for the moving of the stones they appear in, through the use of ropes. There were also some attempts to justify the presence of this hallmark, claiming they are for lifting, but instead of ropes, through the use of wood frames that would lock on the nubs. However, nubs are often (though by no means exclusively) found at the base of the structures they appear in, no matter where the structure is geographically. This alone negates the academic explanations that they were used for the lifting of the stones, be it by rope, or by wood framing.

Based upon our observations, we, on the other hand, find this to be a complete misinterpretation of what these may actually represent, be it culturally, in possible practical effects, and/or meanings obtainable from their shape, positioning and numbers. We do not deny that there are some, especially in far more recent edifications, that fit the description and interpretation given by academics, but we completely refute that such examples are representative in absolute of the presence of this particular hallmark. Furthermore, these hallmarks can be seen protruding by mere millimetres, to several centimetres. This size differential is relevant because these protuberances were achieved by removing a thickness of equal measure to their size. This in itself shows, or better still, proves, their intentionality and important purpose, that as mentioned before could have been cultural or practical, or perhaps both. Some of the countries where they can be found are: India, Japan, Ethiopia, Turkey, Greece, Italy, England, Peru, Bolivia, China, Lebanon.

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Semi circular Nubs

Square Nubs

Rectangular Nubs

Triangular Nubs

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INVERTED NUBS

Although included in the hallmark section, these require an additional description. Inverted nubs share all the characteristics of a normal nub, they are found in the same places we expect to see a nub. However, they appear as if the nub was carved into the stone, instead of on its surface. These can be different shapes and sizes as stated in the descriptions of the variations of “nubs” above. These can be found in Egypt, India and Peru to name but a few.

BEVEL EDGED BLOCKS

Bevel edge blocks have a flat outer layer with the middle of the block extending outward. This can be flat or puffy in nature, as if the surface treatment of this specific hallmark could be changed in accordance with the regional styling used. Although one of the more prevalent within the physical hallmarks, it is also one of the most mysterious. Its use and presence dates back to the oldest structures known to us, into our very recent past, from caves to megaliths, on temples ancient and new, from churches to waterways. This architectural language is predominant, and we are sure of its significance. Even if they have been used merely as a decorative element in more recent years, their roots have a far deeper and meaningful significance. Furthermore, as we will demonstrate, there are combinations of this hallmark with another that whilst assisting in proving their purposeful creation and placement within the structures on which they appear, results in it being somewhat harder to understand their meaning. Their physical presence has been recorded in Turkey, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Jordan, Israel, and Lebanon

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BEVEL EDGED NUB BLOCKS

This hallmark, similarly to that which precedes it, brings a further depth in complexity into the bevel edged block hallmark. Whilst providing further proof of their intentionality and purpose, it becomes more difficult to decipher the latter. Importantly, we note that there are different variations of this hallmark, with obvious similarities to the bevel edge block. As demonstrated in the example pictured below, there is also a nub in the middle of the block. Within its variations, we may see the middle of the block pitted and not flat as shown in the example here. These hallmarks present variations that are not just represented worldwide, they also vary on specific individual temples.

POLYGONAL STONEWORK

Polygonal walls are traditionally classified into three styles that can usually be dated according to their size and joint perfection. In general, the larger and better engineered, the older they are. The first style is constructed with small blocks with coarse and inaccurate joints. The second style shows a good stonework with few wedge fillings between, but only medium size blocks. Finally, of most interest to us is a block which is, for want of a better word, perfect. These joints are so accurately cut that it is impossible to insert a sheet of paper, or the blade of a pocket knife, between two adjacent stones. This final polygonal stonework, was made with cyclopean style stones, all differing in shape and size, that when interlocking with each other, create a vibration resistant wall. The blocks used range in weight from one ton to fifty tonnes in some cases.

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NUB POLYGONAL STONework

Nub polygonal stonework is, of course, polygonal stonework where nubs appear. However, with this hallmark variation, we can see often different shapes, sizes and placements of the nubs; in some cases you may have one, two, three, or four nubs per block. The size of the megalithic blocks also varies from one to fifty tonnes, and sometimes reaching one hundred tonnes. The placement and weight of these megalithic stones once again suggests that they were not for lifting.

LOZENGES

This diamond-shaped-like motif dates back, at the very least, to the paleolithic age. It appears not only globally, but seemingly having the same symbolic value wherever it is found. From cave walls to small objects of fine craftsmanship, these ancient rhombus patterns are often seen in diamond vault stylisation, traditional costume patterns of Slavic people, and traditional Ukrainian embroidery. In 1658, the English philosopher Sir Thomas Browne, published “The Garden of Cyrus”, subtitled “The Quincansior Rhombus” or “The Network Plantation of the Ancients”. In it, he described the five-pointed star, as he outlined the mysterious interrelationships between art, nature, and the universe through these patterns. The rhombus, as it is also known, appears as a symbol in ancient classical elemental systems, amulets, and religious symbolism. These are diamond shaped hallmarks, that as stated, are found across the globe, but not alone, since they are often seen alongside the other hallmarks presented in this work. As a final note for now, they are usually referred to as a star alignment marker, left to us from a specific set of engineers that globally studied the movement of the stars for specific purposes.

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FILLER STONES

A very precisely fitted stone, that is exponentially smaller than the other blocks within the structures where they are found. Usually, if not always, they are in mortar free edifications, whose level of precision within its joints is so extreme that neither a pocket knife blade, nor a piece of paper would fit in between, as with the polygonal stonework hallmark. A clear evidence of their (still unclear) functionality is that, in order for each one to be placed, one or more extremely large blocks, had to be cut in the exact shape and size of the filler block itself. Some might think it the other way round, but by looking at these monumental walls, we find them cut and placed with such level of precision that to suggest that Filler Stones are just a plug for a mistake, its but a poor conclusion in face of the many evidences stating otherwise. Its also important to mention that their placement worldwide is an obvious marker of a specific building technique. Examples of this engineering feature have been documented in Albania, Algeria, Armenia, Bosnia, Cambodia, Croatia, Easter Island, Egypt, Ethiopia, Greece, India, Israel, Italy, Japan, Lebanon, Peru, Syria and Turkey.

PINCH HOLES

Two precisely made holes identical to each other that appear globally at different temples. Some researchers suggest these were used to insert either ropes or metal rings in order to tie animals to them. However, the study of this hallmark shows many examples that are incompatible with this interpretation. Many examples of the hallmark are found one hundred metres high, others are inside temples, and others that are found in cave systems that are not conducive to this analogy. This hallmark appears in China, Greece, Egypt, Turkey, India, Iran, Israel, Japan, Jordan, Malta, Mexico, Peru, Spain, Portugal and England.

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CHAKANA

This hallmark is also referred to as incised motif or stair step motif. As the name suggests, it looks similar to a stair step. Its presence in ancient structures is globally seen and used in different ways. As with several other hallmarks mentioned in this paper, these are clear expressions identifying that very same global culture we have exposed within this paper. Although it is one of the less understood thus far, we are sure that as with all the others, this hallmark is a clear signature of a builder, or of a concept of building, that will be intimately related to all others that appear in the same structure

FLIGHTLESS BIRD

This hallmark is also referred to as incised motif or stair step motif. As the name suggests, it looks similar to a stair step. Its presence in ancient structures is globally seen and used in different ways. As with several other hallmarks mentioned in this paper, these are clear expressions identifying that very same global culture we have exposed within this paper. Although it is one of the less understood thus far, we are sure that as with all the others, this hallmark is a clear signature of a builder, or of a concept of building, that will be intimately related to all others that appear in the same structure.

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DOUBLE SERPENT MOTIF

Much could be said here of this hallmark, one of the best known as the global nature of the double serpent motif, is for all to see among the thousands of examples used worldwide. Its representation and use come from the most ancient past, all the way into the present, from the oldest, highly ritualistic and symbolic representations, whose value is priceless to us, to modern logos in private, governmental and scientific enterprises. Its significance is of such value that, even today, its presence and underlying uses are mystical in nature.

SCRAPE MARKS

This hallmark is quite impressive as it looks so vicious, as if made by a creature with huge claws, hence why it is also named as claw marks. These representations can be found all over the world, from surface temples to the depths of underground caves. It is almost as if a hot knife has cut through butter, when in reality, these blocks are often made in andesite, one of the hardest stones according to the Mohs Scale. They can also be found in differing mineralogies, of varying levels within the Mohs Scale. As to where they are positioned and perhaps more importantly, how they were created, this is still a matter for debate. This can be found in India, Egypt, Portugal, Mexico and South Africa.

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KEYSTONE CUT BLOCKS

Another of the well-known and recognized hallmarks since their presence is easily detected by even the most unobservant visitors to the sites in which they present themselves. It is also important to remember that this hallmark appears in three variations, some of the keystone cut blocks are stone, others are wooden and finally they can also be metallic. As for the implications these variations may have, further analysis is still required, especially as it was used for millennia, crossing the eons of time into recent edifications of now gone civilisations. Their presence can be seen in Ethiopia, India, Bolivia, Japan, Egypt, Iran, Cambodia, Greece, Tunisia, Italy and Peru.

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GLOBAL PRESENCE

Now that we have exposed what we refer to as the global ancient hallmarks (GAH), shown their different configurations and characteristics, and even their possible functionalities, be it in a combined or individual fashion; it is now time to present the evidence of their presence all around the world. This is a vital point of this Statement of Significance, since it serves as irrefutable evidence for the claimed global culture, or, as mentioned, of its global influence at a planetary level though the ages. This is where we put together each individual GAH shown and we correlate them to the specific temples and megalithic sites where they are present, therefore showing their presence across the globe.

NUBS

Semi-Circular Nub

As seen at the Ollantaytambo's Wall of the Six Monoliths, one of the most iconic and baffling pieces of Inca architecture yet to be decoded. Standing approximately 36 feet (11metres) wide and 14 feet (4.2 metres) high, the wall is one of the great mysteries of the Andes. It consists of 6 massive andesite monoliths, which are curiously divided by small strips. It is important to note that not only nubs but other hallmarks appear, as can be clearly seen below the stair step incised motif or chakana. Again, the fact that the rock surface must be removed in order to leave the hallmarks seen here, is in itself proof of intentionality, and not an accident or an imperfection.

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Square Nub

The square nub seen at the Brihadishvara Temple, called Rajarajesvaram by its builder, and known locally as Thanjai Periya Kovil (Thanjavur Big Temple) and Peruvudaiyar Kovil, is a Shaivite Hindu temple built in the Chola architectural style, located on the south bank of the Cauvery river in Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu, India. This location as with many others in India, has incorporated in its structure, all variations of nubs as we have outlined above. They can be seen both in the temple's entrance and throughout the temple. Note that the blocks shown below with the nub hallmark are small and therefore would not require modification for what is wrongly identified as a lifting mechanism.

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The Rectangular Nubs

The Belevi Mausoleum is one of the largest mausoleums in Anatolia, second only to the Mausoleum of Halicarnassus, which it resembles. It is also the second highest tomb house of ancient Anatolia. The influence of this tomb seems to have been widespread throughout the Hellenistic world, exercising directly or indirectly, its influence in the design and construction of other royal tombs. According to archaeological dating of ornaments and ceramics from the monument, the mausoleum was erected around 301BC-281BC. If this date is correct, then the hallmarks that we see worldwide and that are identical to the ones found at this and many other similar sites all over India, serve as physical evidence to the significance of these global architectural elements that thus need to be looked at again. They (GAH) provide a complete new level of information that should be considered when studying the ancient world

One example found at this location are the bevel edge nub blocks, these have pitted middles and standardised semicircular nubs. Underneath these, we can see other blocks, thinner in nature and in them we can also observe rectangular nubs. The lower blocks also show the bevel edged surface. A fine example of multiple uses of the GAH at one site.

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Triangular Nubs

The Acropolis of Athens and its monuments are universal symbols of the classical spirit and civilisation of ancient Greece. It stands as the greatest architectural and artistic complex bequeathed by Greek Antiquity to the world. In the second half of the fifth century BC, Athens, following the victory against the Persians and the establishment of democracy, took a leading position amongst the other city-states of the ancient world. In the age that followed, as thought and art flourished, an exceptional group of artists put into effect the ambitious plans of the Athenian Statesman, Pericles, under the inspired guidance of the sculptor Pheidias, they transformed what was a bare rocky hill, into a unique monument of thought and art. The most important monuments were built during that time: the Parthenon, built by Ictinus, the Erechtheon, the Propylaea, the monumental entrance to the Acropolis, designed by Mnesicles and the small temple of Athena Nike. In the selected areas below, we can see multiple nubs that appear alone or in twin configuration. The entire Acropolis is covered in this phenomenon both internally and externally, with them found not only on walls, but also on steps and stairwells. Multiple variations of the GAH can all be seen at this site

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Inverted Nubs

The pyramid of Menkaure is the smallest of the three main pyramids of the Giza complex, located on the Giza Plateau in the south-western outskirts of Cairo, Egypt. In it, apart from other hallmarks, we can see inverted nubs. These look like they were not made properly or must have been the object of purposeful removal by force. Some of them look like they have blown up so to speak. It is important here to look at the comparative size of the semi circular nubs to the little girl shown sat down, they are almost as big as she is. Note that nubs are not shown above the base level, thus once more negating their use as a lifting aid, thus conducive to another global meaning that is expressed worldwide within the physical evidence.

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Bevel Edge Blocks

Baalbek is a city located east of the Litani River in Lebanon's Beqaa Valley, about 67 km (42 mi) Northeast of Beirut. It is the capital of Baalbek-Hemel Governorate. In Greek and Roman times, Baalbek was also known as Heliopolis (Ἡλιούπολις, Greek for "Sun City"). The bevel edge blocks are clearly visible alongside the Trillithon Stones. Note that this version is flat, there is also a “puffy” version of this hallmark.

The Royal Kurgan or Tarskiy Kurgan (Ukrainian: І(ЛpQbLHD LUprLi) was built in the distant 4th century BC. However, it still stands as one of the most impressive tumuli (kurgans) of the eastern Crimea. The burial barrow is located in the present-day Kerch (Ukraine) and shows the “puffy” characteristic of the bevel edge block, therefore exemplifying how the surface treatments of the stone could change and vary within this Hallmark.

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Bevel Edge Nub Block

The Western Wall, Jerusalem, often shortened to the Kotel or Kosel, and known in the West as the Wailing Wall shows a flat bevel edge nub block. Remember that this variation is slightly different to that which we looked at in Turkey at Belevi Mausoleum. Also shown is the bevel edge block flat and not puffy like the variation seen at the Royal Kurgen Of Kurch.

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Polygonal Stonework

The Imperial Palace (宮殿, Kyūden) and the headquarters of the Imperial Household Agency, are located in the former Nishinomaru enceinte (West Citadel) of the Edo Castle. The principal buildings of the palace grounds, including the Kyūden (宮殿) main palace, home of the Liaison Conference of the Imperial General Headquarters, were severely damaged by the fire of May 1945. Nevertheless, it still shows a megalithic base of polygonal stonework. A hallmark that can be seen in Peru, India, Sardinia, China and Russia just to name a few. The list goes on throughout the ancient world.

Nubbed Polygonal Stonework

The Sacred Valley in Peru is a location with both polygonal stonework and nubbed polygonal stonework in abundance. The blocks we see today were moved, cut and placed at an elevation of 9000 ft, which is a mystery within itself. Note the positioning of the nubs within the polygonal stonework, as it clearly defies the explanation that they served as anchors for lifting. Not only they are often at the base of each stone, but they are also completely offset from its centre of gravity. If lifted by them, the stone would tumble and fall

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The Lozenge

Archaeologists from the University of Tübingen have found an ancient fragment of ivory belonging to a 40,000 year old animal figurine. Both pieces were found in the Vogelherd Cave in south western Germany, which has yielded a number of remarkable works of art dating to the last Ice Age. The mammoth ivory figurine depicting a lion was discovered during excavations around eighty years ago. One of the earliest depictions of the lozenge hallmark, that can be seen carved on its back. Within this location, there was also found a depiction of a bird that could lead to the flightless bird hallmark, if so, one of the earliest examples of its kind. The lozenge, after extensive research, shows a correlation to the use of the stars to specifically orientate the building of their temples for purposes of their own choosing

Auswahl von Elfenbeinfiguren
vom Vogelherd und Hohle Fels, L max. 7,2 cm

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Filler Stones

At the Coricancha Megalithic Sacred Shrine, "The Golden Courtyard" from Quechua language, we can see a hallmark that is seen globally, as a marker to a specific set of engineers, or engineering skills. As can be seen, the fitment is so precise that you could not get a hair in between the block and those surrounding it. One can say that it almost looks 'fused' into place. How this was done remains a mystery, but the global appearance of this physical evidence proves the same builders used the same technique on both a global and regional scale. Something related to the previous GAH can be perceived, while the key stones are common on the floor, the filler stones are prevalent within walls.

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Pinch Holes

The Tarxien Temples are an archaeological complex in Tarxien, Malta. They date to approximately 3150 BC. The site was accepted as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 1992 along with the other megalithic temples on the island of Malta. At this location, two sets of pinch holes can be seen. These are standardised across multiple ancient sites worldwide, however its function is still somewhat of a mystery. We submit, with the backing of physical evidence, that this hallmark (pinch holes) is found both internally and externally and at varied heights that sometimes reach up to one hundred meters in the air. Whatever its purpose may have been, it certainly was not for the tying of animals at that height, not unless there were dragons upon the Earth.

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Chakana

The Achaemenid Empire of Persia (550 - 330 BC) had an elite corps of heavy infantry that was so effective, it helped them to conquer much of the then known world. Besides being essential on the battle field, these troops also served as the imperial guard. We have beautiful depictions of them upon the walls of the Achaemenid capital city of Susa, Iran. Unfortunately, our historical documentation about them comes from their sworn enemies, the Persians, hardly an unbiased source. The clearly visible chakana is yet another of the GAH that can be also seen in Peru, Egypt, China, Saudi Arabia, Jordan and also Palmyra to name but a few. In the face of such vast representation across the globe, we need to ask, was this yet another global hallmark that followed a specific set of engineering and building schematics that were regionally applied

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The Flightless Bird

Göbekli Tepe is a site of monumental megalithic structures, indicated as being built by engineers in the Pre-Pottery Neolithic age. It features limestone T-shaped pillars with images of wild animals. What did these animals actually mean? However, one of these is of special importance for this Statement of Significance, the flightless bird; whose presence, as with all other GAH, can be seen globally and adds to this mystery of engineering. This site is considered as one of the most advanced and ancient temples in the world and yet, as we discussed earlier, this hallmark was passed down long before Göbekli and other near sites. The example we highlighted above within the Volgograd caves is over forty thousand years old.

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The Double Serpent Motif and the Ouroboros

These GAH can be described as two enigmatic and emblematic serpent representations of both ancient Egypt and Greece. The Ouroboros serpent, with its tail in its mouth, continually devouring itself and being reborn at the same time. This has been recognised as a gnostic and alchemical symbol. The Ouroboros expresses the unity of all things, material and spiritual, which never disappears but perpetually repeats itself. If we had to summarise it, we could with confidence say it represents the endless cycles of time. On the other hand, the double-headed serpent is a symbol of Aztec commerce. On the particular example shown in the image below, we identify the effort made to incorporate within this artefact materials that extend far outside of the commonly known borders of the Aztecs and even shells that academics think relate it to the ocean. The blue Turquoise, the serpent's prominent mosaic material, was mined in the area of modern-day south-western United States and the pine and copal resins confirm interior forested domains. All of which reflects the powerful trade networks the Aztecs once controlled. But was it just that? If so, why do we see this hallmark appearing globally? A GAH that when applied on a global scale, with thousands of examples from multiple civilisations, might represent a global symbol of commerce reaching as far back as records go? This would then suggest that engineering and logistics were prevalent on a global scale with these distant cultures working closely together and using a common sign for identification.

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Scrape Marks

This Hallmark extends through time from the very old dates indicated for the Rising Star Caves, then occupied from early Hunter Gatherers, to much more recent examples. For instance, as can be seen in the image below, it looks like a hot knife has gone through butter, only these are andesite blocks. This image is from the Nageshwara twin temple in India. What was capable of doing this? Another GAH that requires a set of engineering skills and equipment that we are yet to understand.

Nageshwara and Channakeshava Twin Temples
Mosale, Karnataka 573120, India

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Keystone Cut Blocks

Although the last of our list, this hallmark is one of the more prevalent within the ancient world, and one that uses different materials in combination with the stone in which they are carved. These variations are very important to remember when looking at the keystone cut hallmark. Despite the different shapes mentioned, the material that actually makes the key changes can be wood, metal of different compositions and also stone. From the many papers within archaeoacoustics, we see that in some cases, for the use of this technology, the stones should be prevented from vibrating and thus avoid absorption of the vibrational input from faults, underwater ways and their combination with telluric energies.

“This is due to the fact that the blocks are fitted together, but without cement. This fact dampens the vibrations from underground and confirms the seismic character of this building that still stands after thousands of years and many earthquakes.”

Paolo Debertolis, Daniele Gullà - 2015

The absence of vibrational loss causes a much stronger output from the stones themselves. This can be verified among many of the 280 plus papers we are adding to this S.O.S. in the Bibliography. Does this mean that some sort of circuit could have been present?

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Conclusion

Swedish archaeologist J. Goldhahn (2002: 41), quoting reputed authors such as Tilley, Nash and Ouzman argues that:

"Bodily experiences of a place are vital for the interpretation of the prehistoric mindscape, of that landscape."

We have, throughout this document, shown physical evidence of a set of markers that were left to us by an ancient culture that somehow, if not globally present, served at the very least as inspiration to most if not all other cultures of which we are aware today. What should be done is to add this new and unexplored set of markers into the list of items that must be sought after, identified and studied according to their high significance. Due to their use in the recent past, especially by religious powers, in their magnificent edifications, we know that although not recognised or studied by academics, some of their meaning and significance was kept by these institutions of a spiritual nature. Temples and cathedrals were built more recently with many of these hallmarks in mind. Is this just a manifestation of a Cargo Cult, where the actual meaning was lost, while its symbolic presence was kept? There are many questions unanswered within this new and vast area of research. Why was so much additional work and resources used to have these GAH in place? What effects do these hallmarks have on the human condition, be it spiritually, physically, or even mentally? We now know that these sites can produce effects upon the human psyche, effects that were replicated in labs within acoustic rooms. There is no doubt, either to us or to other researchers, be them academic or independent, that the frequencies we are recording at these ancient sites produce a direct effect in the biosphere and humans, are an important part of it.

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Bibliography

Due of vast the number of sources used during the research for this document, something that is the product of several years of multidisciplinary research, it become for us virtually impossible to describe them all in this section in a traditional way. Therefore, and because all of them are here used as a support made of empirical peer reviewed evidences, a solution was needed, not only for us to present such sources, but also so that all that wish to consult them, may actually do so without suffering the time consuming process of search. For those reasons we have decided to create a on-line archive where all these papers, scientific articles and publications are readably accessible by the use of a simple QR Code or though the link beneath it.

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1zzTBc6qEzj-4Ye2o2qzXCUi_CDMMGbDA?usp=sharing